

D5.6

List of planned participation in events (Revised version)

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101005931

Project Acronym	YouCount
Project Name	YouCount – Empowering youth and cocreating social innovations and policymaking through youth-focused citizen social science
Grant Agreement no.	101005931
Start date of the project	01 / 02 / 2021
End date of the project	30 /01 /2024
Work Package producing the document	WP-5, Dissemination, exploitation and communication
WP Leader	5, FD
Other Partners involved	1, OsloMet
Deliverable identifier	5.6
Deliverable lead beneficiary	5, FD
Internal Scientific Reviewer	KTU, Egle Butkeviciene
Due date	31, July, 2021 – Revised version: 15, January, 2023
Date of delivery	Date of submission (to be filled by Coordination Office)
Version	Last version as approved by WP-Leader
Author(s)	5, FD, 1, OsloMet
Classification	Public

Disclaimer: This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No101005931. The opinions expressed in this document reflect only the author’s view and reflects in no way the European Commission’s opinions. The European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

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D5.6 List of planned participation in events (Revised version)

The DoA added a new deliverable to the ones already defined in the project proposal: D.5.6. List of planned participation in events. According to the DoA, this Deliverable is an attachment to the DEC- plan¹ and therefore it is intimately linked to it. It will establish the means to encourage partners to identify their participation in the planned activities as defined in table 6 of the DEC plan, ‘Targets for key dissemination activities’. After the mid-term review of the Deliverable in Month 18, the reviewers requested a revision of deliverable. The requirement consisted of adding (1) the list of events in which the project had participated so far; and (2) the list of events in which the project plans to participate.

Therefore, the main objective of this deliverable is to set out the strategy to report on the participation of the planned events, to monitor the dissemination activities linked to these events, to make sure that it happens along the lines of the DEC Plan and to add the list of events the consortium partners have participated so far and plan to participate from now on.

Table 1: Revision history

VERSION	DATE	CREATED BY	COMMENTS
1.0	02 / 07 / 2021	5, FD, Usue Lorenz	First draft with structure and content.
2.0	02 / 01 / 2023	5, FD, usue Lorenz	Second draft of the revised document
3.0	12/01/2023	1, OsloMet, Reidun Norvoll 5, FD, Usue Lorenz	Third draft of the revised document
4.0	16/01/2023	7, KTU, Egle Butkeviciene	Final version of the revised document

¹ Canto-Farachala P., Lorenz, U., Franco, S., Brounéus, F., Norvoll, R. and Hummer, P. YouCount. D.5.7 Continuous, updated DEC and stakeholder engagement plan, and report on DEC activities. Zenodo. doi.10.5281/zenodo.4812107

Cited as: Usue Lorenz, Patricia Canto, Susana Franco, & Reidun Norvoll. (2021). *D5.6 List of Planned Participation in Events (Revised version)*. Zenodo. 10.5281/zenodo.7540776

Table 2: Terms and Abbreviations

ABBREVIATION	FULL TERM
AB	Advisory Board
DEC	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication
DoA	Document of Action
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	General Assembly
LL	Living Lab
SwafS	Science with and for Society
WP	Work Package
YCS	Young citizen scientist

Executive Summary

The DoA added a new deliverable to the ones already defined in the project proposal: D.5.6. List of planned participation in events. According to the DoA, this Deliverable is an attachment to the DEC- plan and therefore it is intimately linked to it. It will establish the means to encourage partners to identify their participation in the planned activities as defined in table 6 of the DEC plan, 'Targets for key dissemination activities'. Therefore, the main objective of this deliverable is to set out the strategy to report on the participation of the planned events, to monitor the dissemination activities linked to these events, to make sure that it happens along the lines of the DEC Plan and to add the list of events the consortium partners have participated so far and plan to participate from now on.

1 Introduction

YouCount's DEC strategy seeks to maximise the overall impact of the project and it sets out the dissemination strategy which aims at engaging with key citizen scientists and other stakeholders at the local, national and global levels to facilitate the scaling up of the project's main findings. Dissemination will be about making available the results of the project as soon as possible to a diverse set of stakeholders.

In this document, events are defined as a set of virtual or physical spaces in which the research team performs dissemination activities and engages in a dialogue around the project's results with YouCount's different target groups at various territorial levels (local, national, European). In section 6, the DEC Plan envisages the main type of activities foreseen for the deployment of the project's dissemination strategy, such as: publications, presentations, scientific sessions, trainings, conferences, etc. However, there is only a generic identification of the events that need to be concretised.

This deliverable aims at setting up a process of continuously tracking the events in which YouCount engages to set-up a dialogue with different stakeholders and at establishing a monitoring system that will allow the Consortium to define a strategic approach to the participation in events as defined earlier. It will inform both the DEC strategy and the Evaluation and impact assessment (WP4).

The first version of the Deliverable came in an early phase of the project (July 2021, M6) and it was focused on establishing structures and procedures for tracking and planning events. The main structure established for this purpose was the YouPlan tool (see version 1 of the Deliverable). However, at this stage of the project, 2023 being the last implementation year, it is crucial to plan the actions to maximise scientific and social impact of YouCount, including not only the participation in events but also other dissemination events, research results and others.

Thus, as it is described in the following section, this revised version of D.5.6 List of Events includes the improved YouPlan version, YouPlan 2.0. It was updated in June 2022, for turning it into a tool to keep track of all YouCount communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities. In summary it presents the following improvements:

- It allows reporting on different types of activities that include events, dissemination activities (excluding events and publications), project results and social media information.
- It includes a planning table of events the partners are planning to participate in.
- It is a tool that will support impact measurement of the project during the project implementation.
- It allows monitoring how project partners are doing in dissemination activities and thus, it enables reflecting on how the project partners need to strengthen their efforts.

This Deliverable is an expanded and improved version of the deliverable of January 2023, targeting better the objectives of the project at this stage. The document is structured as follows: section 2 introduces the improved version of the YouPlan tool to enable tracking and planning of the dissemination, communication and exploitation activities of YouCount; section 3 describes the procedure that the partners are following for keeping track of the DEC activities and their planning; and, the final section includes (i) a list of events that the Consortium partners had participated so far; and (ii) a list of events they plan to participate from December 2022 onwards.

2 YouPlan: Planning & Reporting Tool for Participation in Events

YouPlan is the planning and reporting tool for planning and tracking the planned participation in events. As defined in the DEC Plan, “In order to monitor the effectiveness of our DEC activities, YouCount will collect and monitor quantitative indicators and conduct qualitative measures from the target stakeholder groups. Partners will keep track of all YouCount communication, dissemination and exploitation activities other than standard social media and website interaction in a shared template that will be used for both monitoring and periodic reporting on DEC activities” (page 28, section 10. Monitoring and Evaluation of the D5.7 DEC Plan). Therefore, YouPlan was meant to become YouCount’s Dissemination Activity Tracker allowing YouCount partners that carry out a specific action (i.e. press release, article, flyer, social media post, publication in their newsletter or website, writing scientific articles, etc.) to add a new entry on the tool including some basic information about the action and lessons learnt.

The YouPlan 2.0 version is now formed by four different forms for keeping track of DEC activities and a table for planned events as shown below. Each of the forms contains the links where the information on the data collected is shown.

1. Form 1: to report **undertaken events**

Link: <https://forms.gle/p1C97ea5w9PUzJhr6>

Type of events covered:

- National conference
- International conference /
- Scientific session
- National or international workshop
- Lecture on CSS or training
- YouCount final conference

- Lls training
- training sessions YCS in research teams
- Dialogical Forums
- Communication Activity from Dialogical Forums
- General public event/meeting
- Brokerage event
- Pitch Event
- Trade Fair
- Activities organised jointly with other EU projects

2. Table 1: to report **planned events**

Link: bit.ly/3WDzgGL

Type of events covered:

- National conference
- International conference /
- Scientific session
- National or international workshop
- Lecture on CSS or training
- YouCount final conference
- Lls training
- training sessions YCS in research teams
- Dialogical Forums
- Communication Activity from Dialogical Forums
- General public event/meeting
- Brokerage event
- Pitch Event
- Trade Fair
- Activities organised jointly with other EU projects

3. Form 2: to report on **undertaken dissemination activities (excluding events and publications)**

Link: <https://forms.gle/jtSsTcmPr8sSdbVp9>

Type of undertaken dissemination activities covered:

- Press release
- Exhibition
- Flyer
- University/ Institutional Social Media (e.g. new YouCount institutional twitter account)
- Blog Posts in YouCount's Website
- Communication Campaign (radio, tv)

- Video / film
- Media coverage
- Non-scientific /non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)
- Podcasts
- Local dissemination activity
- Other

4. Form 3: to report on **results of the project** (knowledge generation)

Link: <https://forms.gle/jwqpJtifnCU4dkGE8>

Type of results of the project covered:

- Policy brief
- Research collaboration
- New funding opportunities
- Teaching module
- Report
- Publication
- Thesis (a master, PhD, BA)
- Other. Please specify:

5. Form 4 – social media

Link: <https://forms.gle/cg8u49h2FQ8CmLB5A>

Information covered: Social Media data from project partners

3. Process of planning and tracking the participation in planned events

As described before, events constitute the place where the main dissemination activities take place (presentations, scientific sessions, national workshops, integration of formal education, etc.) and where the research team engages in a dialogue around the main results of YouCount with key stakeholders at the local, national and global levels. Even if YouPlan 2.0 has expanded to integrate the DEC activities, the procedure established in M6 is still in force and running.

In order to enable that the Consortium members think strategically about said events and reflect on which are the events in which the consortium could jointly participate, a three step-logic process for planning and monitoring was set up early in July 2021 to:

- Monitor and report to the European Commission on the participation in events.
- Analyse the strategic presence of YouCount in local, national and global events of different nature (with stakeholders, academics...).
- Plan the participation in the most relevant events where the project's results could be disseminated, specially encouraging joint collaborative dissemination initiatives among the consortium members and Young Citizen Scientists (YCS).

Figure 1. The process of tracking the participation in planned events

1. Planning

Objective: Planned participation in events is reported periodically by the research teams, including the YCS. Each team is expected to reflect on where are the events in which YouCount should have presence at the local, national and global levels. It will allow the Consortium to conduct a strategic reflection on where to participate and also on the potential for joint collaboration.

How:

- The YouPlan monitoring system will allow the periodical reporting of the planned participation in events by the different research. Research members will be required to fill the form 1 on events.
- The data compiled will be analysed and presented to reflect on the events in which YouCount should participate and on how to approach participation.

When:

- Reporting on the planned events will be required for every reporting period (periodically). This reflection will coincide with the internal and official reporting periods fixed by the Consortium and according to the calendar defined in the Appendix G of D6.1 Project Execution Handbook:

Table 3. Reporting periods

Reporting period	Month – before:
1 At the submission of the deliverable	31 Jul, 2021
2 First Internal reporting	1 Dec, 2021
3 Mid-reporting period EC	1 Sep, 2022
4 Second Internal reporting	1 jun, 2023
5 Final reporting EC	1 Mar, 2024

- The analysis derived from the data reported in YouPlan will be presented in the Consortium meetings every six months as defined in Appendix H of D6.1 Project Execution Handbook. Presenting this analysis is meant to stimulate a debate on whether the Consortium is participating or not in the most relevant events or whether further actions should be taken to strengthen YouCount’s participation in events and how. Table 5 below, presents the calendar in which said analysis will be presented.

Table 4. Time schedule for the reflection on the participation in events

Consortium Meeting	Month:
1 Consortium meeting	M8
2 Consortium meeting	M13
3 Consortium meeting	M17
4 Consortium meeting	M22

5	Consortium meeting	M26
6	Consortium meeting	M32

2. Reporting

Objective: continuous reporting on partners' participation in events will be required together with evidence of participation.

How:

- Partners are expected to report on their participation in events as soon as possible after the event is celebrated.
- Partners will be required to fill in Form number 1, for reporting of the events they have participated in.

When: project implementation phase.

3. Following-up

Objective:

- To monitor how the research team is performing regarding the objectives of planned participation in events and report to EB /GA / EC

How:

- The WP leader, FD (number 5), will present at the Consortium meeting how YouCount is meeting said objectives.
- All the partners will report on their participation in events through the means provided.

When: in the Consortium meetings listed in table 5 and together with the reflection based on the Planning of the participation in events

4. Updated list of events

This deliverable, as it is described in the DoA, aims to define the concrete events that consortium partners participate in during the project period to increase impact of the project. The list included in this deliverable does not include the local internal research events foreseen or held in YouCount such as Living lab meetings, dialogues forum, CSS trainings and national workshops related to each case (N= 9) because they are work in progress. The internal events will be collected for the impact assessment exercise through the YouPlan tool. Subsequently, we have only included YouCount events on EU and national project level events targeting a broader group of stakeholders (national and international conferences and workshops such as the ECSA workshop, general public events and the final conference). This means that the total amount of planned YouCount events in 2023 is more extensive than can be seen from Appendix B. The list provided in Appendix A and B reflect the current status of the events the partners have participated in and a list of events the partners are planning to participate early in 2023. This last event list is ongoing work and the consortium partners could add additional or remove events during the spring as part of their research activities. There will be an update of the list of events as part of the internal reporting period for the YouCount project June 2023.

Appendix A includes a list of events in which the Consortium partners had participated by January 2023. In summary, some conclusions and clarifications on these events are:

- The Consortium members have participated in 13 international and national conferences (22 events were committed in the DoA), 3 scientific sessions (covering the objectives in the DoA) and 7 national and international workshops.
- Regarding the 7 National and international workshops reported, 4 are national and 3 international, on the top of the objectives that were defined in the DoA (9 national workshops in each participating country as part of the internal research activities). Thus, the partners are participating in more workshops than initially expected.
- The consortium was committed to participate 9 Lectures on CSS and they have already organised 8.
- On the general public events, 5 events were reported so far. Efforts need to be addressed by all partners to reach the numbers defined in the DoA (11 general public events).
- On the top of the events in which the partners were committed to participate, additional efforts have been addressed to connect with other related EU projects through the participation in 5 events from other EU projects.
- In addition to what is included in the list of reported events, the consortium partners have participated in 16 Science with and for Society (SWAFS) meetings by M18, including chairing and presenting the YouCount project in the October meeting, 2022.

Appendix B includes a list of planned events in which the project currently plans to participate. The list is 1) based on the initial list of events included in the DoA as interesting and ongoing plans and 2) suggestions of the partners on the participation in events reported in YouPlan by January 2023, where partners were asked to prioritise the most important conferences to target to maximise scientific and social impact.

The conclusions and clarifications on the list of planned events reported by January the 10th of 2023 are the following ones:

- The Consortium intensifies its planned participation in events in the categories that have to do with national and international conferences, national policy conferences and national workshops (15, 2 and 3 events planned in each category respectively). As mainly international conferences have been planned, the partner need to reflect on which national conferences they will participate in.
- Regarding the scientific sessions, YouCount has planned to organise monthly scientific sessions addressing challenges related to CSS. We have defined approximately 6 planned events of this category, but it is probable that there will be more.
- However, they need to intensify the participation in events in the category general public event as only one is planned for 2023 and 5 reported so far.

In order to respond to the EC requirement on adding the updated version, these lists have been updated during January 2023 by the Consortium partners and included in Appendix A and B.

Appendixes

Table 5: Appendixes

APPENDIX	SUBJECT	PAGE
Appendix A	List of events in which the Consortium partners have participated	17
Appendix B	List of events in which the project currently plans to participate	25

Appendix A. List of events in which the Consortium partners have participated

No.	Type of event reported	Role of the participant	Name of the event:	Event start date:	Event end date	Place/ institution where the event took place	Type of audience	Link to dissemination and YouCount's event material
1	National conference	Prese ntation	I Encuentro Nacional de Ciencia Ciudadana, Ciencias Sociales y Humanidades	23/09/ 2021	23/09/202 1	Ibercivis, Zaragoza	Scientific community (Higher Education and Research), Other CS projects (i.e. Swafs Community), Research councils and science communication institutions, General public	https://ciencia-ciudadana.es/i-evento-cc-y-ssh/
2		Prese ntation	Citizen Science in Norway (transl.)	19/11/ 2021	19/11/202 1	Oslo, Norway + online	Scientific community (Higher Education and Research), Other CS projects (i.e. Swafs Community), Research councils and science communication institutions	Material: https://www.forskningradet.no/arrangementer/2021/folkeforskning-i-norge/ Social media channels, https://twitter.com/youcountproject/status/1462800448822390786
3		Prese ntation	XVI Congreso de la Asociación Española de Ciencia Política (AECPA)	07/09/ 2022	09/09/202 2	Universitat de Girona/University of Girona (Girona, Spain).	Scientific community (Higher Education and Research), Other CS projects (i.e. Swafs Community)	https://aecpa.es/es-es/co-construyendo-ciudadania-a-traves-de-la-aplicacion-de-la-ciencia-ciu/congress-papers/3666/
1	Internation al conference	Prese ntation	Engaging Citizen Science Conference 2022	25/05/ 2022	26/05/202 2	Aarhus University	Scientific community (Higher Education and Research)	https://www.essrg.hu/en/engaging-citizen-science-conference-2022/ Material: https://conferences.au.dk/citsci2022/programme
2		Prese ntation	Engaging Citizen Science Conference 2022, April 25-26, Aarhus, Denmark	25/04/ 2022	26/04/202 2	Aarhus University, Aarhus, Denmark	Scientific community (Higher Education and Research)	https://conferences.au.dk/user_upload/CitSci (Link to PDF: https://webcache.googleusercontent.com/search?q=cache:S9xQm9A9Op4J:https://conferences.au.dk/fileadmin/user_upload/CitSci/Engaging_Citizen_Science_Conference2022_Booklet.pdf+&cd=3&hl=de&ct=clnk&gl=at&client=firefox-b-d)
3		Prese ntation	The race of Citizen Science: Pitch your project in 3 minutes! The YouCount project. SwafS Citizen Science Working Group	20/01/ 2021	20/01/202 1	online	Scientific community (Higher Education and Research), Other CS projects (i.e. Swafs Community)	NA

■ YouCount | D5.6 List of planned participation in events (revised version)

No.	Type of event reported	Role of the participant	Name of the event:	Event start date:	Event end date	Place/ institution where the event took place	Type of audience	Link to dissemination and YouCount's event material
4		Prese- ntation , Partici- pation	Understanding the conceptual relations between social innovation and citizen social science: Results from systematic literature review. ESPAnet Conference 2022	31/08/ 2021	03/09/202 1	online	Scientific community (Higher Education and Research), Research councils and science communication institutions	NA
5		Organi- sation, Prese- ntation , Partici- pation	9th International Conference in Community Psychology (9ICCP)	21/09/ 2022	24/09/202 2	University of Naples Federico II - Naples, IT	Scientific community (Higher Education and Research), Policymakers and community stakeholders, employers and end user organisations, Young people (including YCS)	NA
6		Prese- ntation	American Anthropological Association Annual Meeting	09/11/ 2022	13/11/202 2	Seattle, Washington state, USA	Scientific community (Higher Education and Research)	NA
7		Prese- ntation , Partici- pation	Oslo Architecture Triennale 2022: Neighbourhoods – public space for everybody. How can we create better, safer and more inclusive public spaces in urban neighbourhoods?	27/10/ 2022	27/10/202 2	The former Munch Museum, Oslo, Norway - organised by Habitat Norge	Policymakers and community stakeholders, employers and end user organisations, General public	1) https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Zkpm058416g&t=4310s 2) https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Zkpm058416g&t=7567s 3) https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Zkpm058416g&t=9125s
8		Prese- ntation , Partici- pation	European Citizen Science Association Conference 2022	05/10/ 2022	08/10/202 2	Museum fuer Naturkunde Berlin, Germany	Scientific community (Higher Education and Research), Other CS projects (i.e. Swafs Community), Research councils and science communication institutions	https://www.facebook.com/youcountproject/posts/pfbid0X4VFWrgHAN2kXjyLj1Vh3yBzP2VvRRP4CEKxySK5nzmnPahSW5gksdYdevznVbbJI?__cft__[0]=AZU-E9vM_N2StZuymMvr78LquynKOEsqxqZMvZs4SH1udUDM-IWvJylqOG4sLyXqFKy3al7gbE_sjWCcfj6JpIYZ7iNgd1e2hA0F_NDpoCHtnniskCV9_wiuagYxwNKqEmvKR5NpYUzmFmPYvNCkH3yk2&__tn__=%2CO%2CP-R
9		Prese- ntation , Partici- pation	"The 28th annual ISDRS Conference: SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT AND COURAGE: CULTURE,	15/06/ 2022	17/06/202 2	Södertörn University, Stockholm, Sweden	Scientific community (Higher Education and Research), Research councils and science communication institutions, Policymakers and community	https://2022.isdrsconferences.org/ Material: https://sh.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:17 https://2022.isdrsconferences.org/https://2022.isdrsconferences.org/18497/FULLTEXT01.pdf

No.	Type of event reported	Role of the participant	Name of the event:	Event start date:	Event end date	Place/ institution where the event took place	Type of audience	Link to dissemination and YouCount's event material
10			ART AND HUMAN RIGHTS"				stakeholders, employers and end user organisations	
		Prese- ntation	9ICCP Naples International conference on community psychology	21/09/2022	24/09/2022	Università degli Studi di Napoli, Federico II;	Scientific community (Higher Education and Research), Research councils and science communication institutions, Policymakers and community stakeholders, employers and end user organisations, Young people (including YCS)	NA
1	Scientific session	Partici- pation	Working with youth at risk of social exclusion. Session 14.10: Citizen science is social! Evening event with hands on citizen science. Citizen science SDG Conference	14/10/2020	15/10/2020	online	Scientific community (Higher Education and Research), Policymakers and community stakeholders, employers and end user organisations, Other	NA
2		Prese- ntation , Partici- pation	Working with youth in transdisciplinary projects for sustainability A SustainLab breakfast seminar	01/12/2021	01/12/2021	Södertörn University, Stockholm, Sweden	Scientific community (Higher Education and Research), Other CS projects (i.e. Swafs Community)	https://acrobat.adobe.com/link/review?uri=urn:aaid:scds:US:f0278f0e-6306-3af1-8f70-d3f6c1b9259a
3		Organi- sation, Prese- ntation	ECSA Citizen Science for Planetary Health	06/10/2022	07/10/2022	Berlin, Natural History Museum	Scientific community (Higher Education and Research), Other CS projects (i.e. Swafs Community)	NA
1	National or international workshop	Partici- pation	YouCount consortium meeting in Copenhagen	07/06/2022	09/06/2022	Aalborg University	Scientific community (Higher Education and Research)	https://www.essrg.hu/en/youcount-team-in-copenhagen/
2		Partici- pation	Network for CS in Norway - working group SSH	07/04/2022	07/04/2022	Research Council of Norway	Scientific community (Higher Education and Research), Research councils and science communication institutions	NA
3		Prese- ntation , Partici- pation	Involve Hub, Ethics and citizens involved science		25/08/2022	Research Council of Norway	Scientific community (Higher Education and Research), Other CS projects (i.e. Swafs Community), Research councils and science communication institutions, Policymakers and community stakeholders,	NA

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No.	Type of event reported	Role of the participant	Name of the event:	Event start date:	Event end date	Place/ institution where the event took place	Type of audience	Link to dissemination and YouCount's event material
							employers and end user organisations	
4		Organisation, Presentation, Participation	EIE WG & YouCount webinars 2021 Webinar 1: Inclusive co-creation in Y-CSS: How to open up research & innovation to young people?	24/09/2021	24/09/2021	Online	Scientific community (Higher Education and Research), Other CS projects (i.e. Swafs Community), Policymakers and community stakeholders, employers and end user organisations, Young people (including YCS)	https://docs.google.com/document/d/1hyJ3Eb2qG3B6a2UkJLnP2zGUr1ssqsrqLPkXO5_K_uk/edit
5		Organisation, Presentation, Participation	WG EIE (ECSA) + YouCount => Webinar 2: Setting up Y-CSS: How to work in inclusive ways?	21/10/2021	21/10/2021	Online	Scientific community (Higher Education and Research), Other CS projects (i.e. Swafs Community), Policymakers and community stakeholders, employers and end user organisations, Young people (including YCS)	https://docs.google.com/document/d/1VXSnEGPkYT_hShjt0L_VNWgPRZaoxqacPSVjRIAfAg/edit
6		Organisation, Presentation, Participation	EIE WG (ECSA) + Youcount: Webinar 3: Transformative & innovative impact of Y-CSS: How to make social change?	04/11/2021	04/11/2021	Online	Scientific community (Higher Education and Research), Other CS projects (i.e. Swafs Community), Policymakers and community stakeholders, employers and end user organisations, Young people (including YCS)	https://docs.google.com/document/d/1rsfU0uCW8n9EHG5GJgJAdbfVuelzhtrD6QxBg5NYTu0/edit
7		Organisation, presentation, participation	"Etikai elvárások és dilemmák a részvételi akciókutatásban" (Ethical expectations and dilemmas in participatory action research)	14/06/2021	14/06/2021	Corvinus University of Budapest	Scientific community + professional in community and organisational development	https://www.essrg.hu/hu/etikai-megfontolasok-es-dilemmak-a-reszveteli-akciokutatasban/
1	Lecture on CSS or training	Presentation	E-sustainability course, Department of Planning, AAU	09/02/2022	24/02/2022	Aalborg University, Copenhagen	Research councils and science communication institutions, Other	https://vbn.aau.dk/da/projects/developing-the-sustainability-e-course-at-the-department-of-plann
2		Organisation, Presentation	Collaboration with local high school	22/02/2022	03/05/2022	Københavns Åbne Gymnasium, Copenhagen	Policymakers and community stakeholders, employers and end user organisations, Young people (including YCS)	NA

No.	Type of event reported	Role of the participant	Name of the event:	Event start date:	Event end date	Place/ institution where the event took place	Type of audience	Link to dissemination and YouCount's event material
3		Prese ntation	Citizen Social Science. The nuts and bolts of citizen science. ECSA, online training programme	16/04/2022	16/04/2022	Ukraine, online	Scientific community (Higher Education and Research), Other CS projects (i.e. Swafs Community), Policymakers and community stakeholders, employers and end user organisations	ECSA webpage
4		Prese ntation	CoAct Citizen Social Science School: S5: Putting Citizen Social Science experiences together: YouCount, COESO, SoCis, ActEarly and CoAct. Presentation Reidun Norvoll and Aina Landsverk Hagen: How to build meaningful engagement in citizen social science projects.	23/09/2021	23/09/2021	Online	Scientific community (Higher Education and Research), Other CS projects (i.e. Swafs Community)	Social media channels, Part of CoAct dissemination events, https://coactproject.eu/citizen-social-science-school-social-dimensions-in-citizen-science/
5		Prese ntation	Meeting with Intercultural Museum	10/06/2021	10/06/2021	Intercultural Museum, Oslo	Policymakers and community stakeholders, employers and end user organisations	NA
6		Prese ntation	Method forum: Participation in social research, what is it and how do we do it? (transl.)	24/11/2021	24/11/2021	OsloMet, Oslo, Norway	Scientific community (Higher Education and Research)	NA
7		Prese ntation	Presentation for service design team at the Norwegian Labour and Welfare Administration (NAV) by Aina Landsverk Hagen and Sara Berge Lorenzen	08/09/2022	08/09/2022	the Norwegian Labour and Welfare Administration (NAV), Oslo, Norway	Policymakers and community stakeholders, employers and end user organisations	NA
8		Organi sation, Prese ntation	UCLAN lecture on CSS	20/10/2022	20/10/2022		Young people (including YCS)	NA
1	General public event/meeting	Organi sation, Prese ntation, Partici pation	Sydhavns Festival	09/06/2022	09/06/2022	Sydhavnen, Copenhagen	Policymakers and community stakeholders, employers and end user organisations, Young people (including YCS), General public	https://sv-festival.dk/musik-miljoe-dag/

■ YouCount | D5.6 List of planned participation in events (revised version)

No.	Type of event reported	Role of the participant	Name of the event:	Event start date:	Event end date	Place/ institution where the event took place	Type of audience	Link to dissemination and YouCount's event material
2		Presentation, Participation	Sydhavns Folkemøde (The peoples meeting in South Harbour)	04/09/2021	04/09/2021	Sydhavnen, Copenhagen	Policy makers and community stakeholders, employers and end user organisations, General public, Other	https://svfolkemode.dk
3		Organisation, Participation	Summer camp in Huset 2450	27/06/2022	29/06/2022	Sydhavnen, Copenhagen	Policy makers and community stakeholders, employers and end user organisations, Young people (including YCS), General public	https://www.facebook.com/events/1748797095463764/?acontext=%7B%22ref%22%3A%2252%22%2C%22action_history%22%3A%22%5B%7B%5C%22surface%5C%22%3A%5C%22share_link%5C%22%2C%5C%22mechanism%5C%22%3A%5C%22share_link%5C%22%2C%5C%22extra_data%5C%22%3A%7B%5C%22invite_link_id%5C%22%3A539337497673951%7D%7D%5D%22%7D
1	Pitch Event	Organisation, Presentation	Pitch for recruiting new YCS	13/05/2022	13/05/2022	online, University of Vienna, Vienna, Austria	Young people (including YCS)	NA
1	Trade Fair	Organisation, Presentation	Workshop 1: Citizen Science Introduction and Survey Creation (YouCount Evaluation)	16/01/2022	16/01/2022	online, University of Vienna, Vienna, Austria	Policy makers and community stakeholders, employers and end user organisations, Young people (including YCS)	NA
1	Activities organised jointly with other EU projects	Presentation	What's new in Citizen Science Training? From Open Science to Public Engagement	27/10/2021	27/10/2021	Online	Scientific community (Higher Education and Research), Other CS projects (i.e. Swafs Community), General public	https://twitter.com/youcountproject/status/1451502183548129280 Material: https://eu-citizen.science/blog/2021/10/05/whats-new-in-citizenscience-training-from-open-science-to-engagement/
2		Presentation	Empowerment, Inclusiveness and Equity ECSA Group	29/11/2022	29/11/2022	Online	Scientific community (Higher Education and Research), Other CS projects (i.e. Swafs Community)	NA
3		Participation	Meetings with the Socio Bee project	19/10/2021	19/10/2021	Deusto, San Sebastian	Scientific community (Higher Education and Research)	NA
4		Participation	Meeting with Socio Bee project	12/05/2022	12/05/2022	Online	Scientific community (Higher Education and Research)	NA
5		Participation	Meeting with Socio Bee project	14/12/2022	14/12/2022	Online	Scientific community (Higher Education and Research)	NA

Appendix B. List of events in which the project currently plans to participate

No	Type of event	Name of the event	Location of the event (City, Country)	Start date	End date	Link to the event	Registration deadline
1	1. Presentation / participation at international and national conferences	American Anthropology Association (AAA) Annual Meeting	Toronto, Canada	2023-11-15	2023-11-19	2023 - joint with the AAA, November 15-19, Toronto	ND
2		METROPOLIS EURA of the European Urban Research Association 2023	Reykjavík, Iceland. University of Iceland - Faculty of Political Science, Faculty of Life and Environmental Sciences and Institute of Public Administration and Politics	2023-06-22	2023-06-24	https://eura.org/news-eura23-savethedate/	
3		The International Association for Media and Communication Research, IAMCR 2023	Lyon, France	2023-07-09	2023-07-13	https://iamcr.org/	26 June to 5 July
4		ICSECT 2023: 17. International Conference on Social, Economic and Cultural Transformations	Oslo, Norway	2023-06-22	2023-06-23	International Conference on Social, Economic and Cultural Transformations ICSECT in June 2023 in Oslo	
5		18th European Congress of Psychology- European Federation of Psychologists' Associations (EFPA), 2023	Brighton, UK hosted by the British	2023-07-03	2023-07-06	European Congress of Psychology EFPA	

No	Type of event	Name of the event	Location of the event (City, Country)	Start date	End date	Link to the event	Registration deadline
			Psychological Society				
6		European Community Psychology Conference (ECPA, 2022)		2023-12-19	2023-12-19	https://www.ecpa-online.com/	
7		ICCP 2023: 17. International Conference on Community Psychology	Amsterdam, Netherlands	2023-05-04	2023-05-05	https://waset.org/community-psychology-conference-in-may-2023-in-amsterdam	
8		YouCount and ECSA WG EIE Workshop	Hybrid Budapest (HU)			In September, final dates and organisations TBD	
9		AMPS Livable Cities	New York, USA	2023-06-14	2023-06-16	Livable Cities Conference New York 2023 AMPS (amps-research.com)	Abstract deadline: 10 April 2023
10		BPS Community Psychology Festival	Edinburgh, UK	tbc	tbc		
11		NCRM Research Methods e-Festival	online	2023-11-23	2023-11-23	Call opens for 2023 Research Methods e-Festival (ncrm.ac.uk)	Application for contributors deadline: 14th Feb 2023
12		I International Congress INFAPOST	Bilbao, Spain	2023-01-19	2023-01-20	https://infapost.es/i-congreso-internacional/	20-12-2022
13		C*Sci 2023	Phoenix, Arizona, US	2023-05-22	2023-05-26	citizenscience.org	NA

No	Type of event	Name of the event	Location of the event (City, Country)	Start date	End date	Link to the event	Registration deadline
14		SIPCO (Italian Society of Community Psychology) conference	Naples, Italy	2023-09-21	2023-09-23	-	Open in http://9iccpnaples.com/call-for-papers/
1	3. Presentations at national policy conferences	IkerGazte 2023. Nazioarteko ikerketa euskaraz	San Sebastian, Spain	2023-05-17	2023-05-19	https://www.ueu.eus/ikergazte/	17-02-2023
2		IX Congreso de la Red Española de Política Social	Palma de Mallorca, Spain	2023-10-25	2023-10-27	https://www.repspalma2023.es/85973/detail/ix-reps-crisis-globales-e-impactos-locales-tendencias-y-respuestas-publico-comunitarias-para-una-tr.html	27-01-2023
1	4. Scientific session at Conferences	YouCount Workshops	Online	6 during 2023		-	
2		Presentation of Heidi Ballard - Consortium Meeting San Sebastian	San Sebastian, Spain	2023-03-22	2023-03-23	-	
1	5. National workshops	ShareGune Orkestra	San Sebastian, Spain	In June. To be specified			None.
2		Knowledgegune, a space for sharing and discussing on research topic in Orkestra Title: Citizen participation in research processes	San Sebastian, Spain	2023-01-13	2023-01-13		
3		Department of social workm Linnéuniversitet/Linnaeus University	Stockholm, Sweden	2023-09-14	2023-09-14		
1	6. Lectures on CSS	Born in Bradford	Bradford, UK	2023-07-06			Invited lecture on YouCount

No	Type of event	Name of the event	Location of the event (City, Country)	Start date	End date	Link to the event	Registration deadline
1	8. FINAL Conference	YouCount project	Hybrid - Brussels, Belgium	2023-12-04	2023-12-05		
1	9. General public events	Lancashire Science Festival	Preston, UK	2023-05-20	2023-05-20	Lancashire Science Festival	

PARTNERS:

